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D1.2 – Data Management Plan

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EU	European
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WB	Work Bench

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project is successor to the Blue-Cloud project which established a cyber platform bringing together and providing access to: 1) multidisciplinary data from observations and models, 2) analytical tools, & 3) computing facilities essential to support research to better understand and manage the many aspects of ocean sustainability. Blue-Cloud 2026 aims at a further evolution of the pilot infrastructure into a Federated European Ecosystem to deliver FAIR & Open data and analytical services, instrumental for deepening research of oceans, EU seas, coastal & inland waters.

Data management is an essential and integrated activity throughout the project lifetime and should be deployed and supported by the Blue-Cloud 2026 services and their evolutions as planned. The data managed by the project and subject to the present DMP include:

- **input data from existing known aquatic data infrastructures**, as managed by project partners and possibly some international data infrastructures, **brought together from various existing sources via the Data Discovery & Access service (DD&AS)**;
- **other input data, uploaded by the user**;
- **resulting datasets/derived datasets, created by users as a result of their usage of Blue-Cloud analytical services**;
- **research outputs and datasets generated by the Blue-Cloud VRE**
- **research outputs and datasets generated by the Blue-Cloud 2026 website.**

This initial Blue-Cloud Data Management Plan (DMP) has been compiled to serve as a guidance giving directions. This DMP follows the Horizon Europe guidelines for Data Management Plans and associated template¹. It is organised around solutions and approaches aiming at making data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR). For that purpose, an overview is given of data (to be) managed by the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and solutions, both ‘existing/already planned’ and ‘possibly to be developed’ are given for applying FAIR principles. In addition, the DMP considers other aspects of data management, such as resources, data security and ethical aspects.

This initial DMP will be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise and/or more insights become available as part of the ongoing developments.

¹ <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>

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1. Introduction

Between 2019 and 2022 the Horizon 2020 pilot Blue-Cloud project (<https://blue-cloud.org/about-h2020-blue-cloud>) developed a collaborative web-based environment providing simplified access to an unprecedented wealth of o multi-disciplinary datasets from observations, analytical services, and computing facilities essential for blue science. The project responded to both the interests of the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), and the [blue research communities](#) and in its latest stage evolved into a thematic marine Open Science platform serving the Blue Economy, Marine Environment and Marine Knowledge agendas. It deployed a smart federation of multidisciplinary data repositories, analytical tools, and computing facilities in support of exploring and demonstrating the potential of cloud based open science for ocean sustainability, UN Decade of the Oceans, and G7 Future of the Oceans. The pilot Blue-Cloud delivered:

- a **Data Discovery & Access service (DD&AS)**, federating key European data management infrastructures, to facilitate users in finding and retrieving multi-disciplinary datasets from multiple repositories;
- a **Virtual Research Environment infrastructure (VRE)** providing a range of services and facilitating orchestration of computing and analytical services for constructing, hosting and operating Virtual Labs for specific applications;
- **Five multi-disciplinary Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs (VLabs)**, configured with specific analytical workflows, targeting major scientific challenges, and serving as real-life **Demonstrators**, which can be adopted and adapted for other inputs and analyses.

Since early 2023, Blue-Cloud 2026 will further evolve into a Federated European Ecosystem to deliver FAIR & Open data and analytical services, instrumental for deepening research of oceans, EU seas, coastal & inland waters.

To serve as a guideline when further developing these services, an initial Blue-Cloud 2026 Data Management Plan (DMP) is drafted in this Deliverable D1.2. This initial DMP follows the Horizon Europe guidelines for Data Management Plans as published by the European Commission. It gives an overview of the type of data (to be) managed by the Blue-Cloud project and identifies solutions, both 'existing/already planned' and 'possibly to be developed' for meeting the FAIR principles, for as far as feasible and required within the scope of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

This initial DMP will be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise and/or more insights become available as part of the ongoing developments.

2. Main datasets generated and managed by Blue-Cloud 2026

One major aim of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project is to evaluate and demonstrate the potential added-value for science of combining multi-disciplinary data sets. Another major aim is to promote web-based science, promoted as a potential benefit of EOSC. Both aims will be supported by the Blue-Cloud 2026 technical framework and should become manifest by developing and showcasing the scientific Virtual Labs, facilitating researchers to combine multi-disciplinary data input from multiple sources and to run efficiently processing pipelines on the cloud, generating useful and interesting data products for several user communities.

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project will further develop the existing Blue-Cloud technical framework as established in the predecessor Blue-Cloud project. This technical framework consists of:

1. **The Blue Cloud data discovery and access service** serves federated discovery and access to blue data infrastructures. The DD&AS already federates multiple leading Blue Data Infrastructures, and facilitates common discovery and access to more than 10 million marine datasets for physics, chemistry, geology, bathymetry, biology, biodiversity, and genomics. It is fully based on machine-to-machine brokering interactions with web services as provided and operated by the Blue Data Infrastructures. As part of Blue-Cloud 2026 it will evolve and expand by federating more leading European Aquatic Data Infrastructures, improving the FAIRness of the underpinning web services, incorporating semantic brokering, and adding data subsetting query services.
2. **The Blue Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)** component provides a versatile Blue Cloud VRE as a federation of computing platforms and analytical services for developing and running the Virtual Labs for the scientific Demonstrators. The Blue-Cloud VRE, powered by **D4Science**, facilitates collaborative research offering computing, storage, analytical, and generic services for constructing, hosting and operating analytical workflows for specific applications. Blue-Cloud 2026 will expand the VRE by federating multiple e-infrastructures and facilitating seamless orchestration of workflows, divided over different e-infrastructures.

The technical framework will support the main flow of marine data from 1) connected European Aquatic Data Infrastructures directly to users, facilitated by the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service, and 2) in the VRE from input to output. Input for VRE operations will be provided by retrieving data sets (including metadata) from the European Aquatic Data Infrastructures, connected to the Blue Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service. Additional input will be provided by users ingesting data sets from other external sources, including their own data sources. The data input can be in-situ data, earth observation data, and model outputs.

Selected input will be used in each of the **Virtual Labs**, as to be upgraded and developed for the scientific demonstrators for further analysis, combining, and processing input using analytical services. These

analytical services can be various algorithms and services. **The results of the analytical processes in the form of data products will be considered as output, that might be published and made available for viewing and downloading.**

Selected input will also be used in each of the **new Blue-Cloud analytical Big Data WorkBenches**. These WorkBenches will be developed, validated, and documented to perform big data analyses in a structural, and reproducible way for generating sets of harmonised and validated data collections for a selection of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs). The plan is that these WorkBenches will be adopted and integrated later on by EMODnet, CMEMS, and selected RIs in their operational processes. The EOVs for physics, chemistry, and biology are highly relevant for analysing the state of the environment and numerical simulations of the planned Digital Twin of the Oceans (DTO). The associated analytical services comprise various algorithms and services. **The results in the form of data products will be considered as output, that might be published and made available for viewing and downloading.**

The Blue-Cloud project itself does not gather observation data about the oceans, rivers, and estuaries, e.g. by measurements or sensors. As a federation of existing aquatic data infrastructures aiming to enable data analyses by its end users, **it brings together data from various existing sources.** The main goal of Blue-Cloud 2026, being to provide users the possibility to process data, the focus is on providing input data, and handling the resulting derived data, which may then be made public. Thus, these groups of data can be identified:

- A. **Input data from existing known aquatic data infrastructures**, as managed by project partners and possibly some international data infrastructures, as managed by non-project partners. This can be divided into:
 - a. Input data that is being kept at the originating aquatic data infrastructures and is transferred to the Blue-Cloud servers only on demand, when a user requests the data to perform processing on it. The originating infrastructures remain responsible for this data and their DMPs are applicable.
 - b. Input data that was copied from the originating infrastructures and stored (and possibly modified) by the Blue-Cloud project, to match the demonstrators.
- B. **Other input data, uploaded by the users.**
- C. **Resulting datasets/derived datasets, created by users as a result of their usage of Blue-Cloud analytical services.**
- D. Data and user information generated within the **Blue-Cloud VRE hosted on the D4Science** infrastructure;
- E. In addition, there is also data generated via **the public Blue-Cloud website** and through the Blue-Cloud outreach activities, such as KPIs on web statistics, number of participants to webinars, etc.

as well as research outputs produced by Blue-Cloud partners in the form of documents and reports. This will also be taken into account in this DMP in section 4

In this DMP, these different groups of data are addressed. The groups (Ab), (B), (C) reside on and are managed by the Blue-Cloud infrastructure. They make up the "VRE data pool". For the (Aa) data, the data management itself (e.g. preservation) is handled by the originating sources, the aquatic data infrastructures. Their FAIRness, and the FAIRness of the federated access in Blue-Cloud, is described in section 3.

2.1. Processes and procedures

As already stated in the Deliverable 1.1 Project Handbook, the Blue-Cloud 2026 Project Coordination (PC) team is data controller and data processor of specific sets of data, as showcased below:

- **CNR** assumes the role of **Data Controller** of any personal data gathered, via the **D4Science** platform, according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679). The Data Processing Officer (DPO) for CNR is the head of the Data Protection office in Rome (email: rpd@cnr.it).
- **Trust-IT** assumes the role of **Data Controller** for any personal data gathered, via the Blue-Cloud 2026 **website** and otherwise, according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679). The Data Processing Officer (DPO) for Trust-IT is: Mr. Michele Nannipieri, (email: m.nannipieri@trust-it-services.com).
- **MARIS** assumes the role of **Data Controller** for any personal data gathered, via the Blue-Cloud 2026 **Data Discovery and Access Service**, according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679). The Data Processing Officer (DPO) for MARIS is Serge van der Horst, (email: serge@maris.nl).

Each Project Partner will assume the role of **Data Processor**, according to the GDPR. This is needed for all partners to contribute to the specific objectives of the project, carrying out the various activities specified by the Grant Agreement with the needed efficiency and incremental value brought to the various datasets involved. To this aim, a Data Processing Agreement (DPA) by each Data Processor with the Data Controller will be added as an Annex to the Collaboration Agreement and approved by all partners during the General Assembly foreseen in November 2023. A copy of such an agreement is enclosed in Annex 1 to this document.

Each WP leader (with the technical qualification of Data Processor) is going to be responsible for data management within the WP, including updates and implementation of the Data Management Plan. The PC team (CNR, Trust-IT, MARIS) assume responsibility for overall data management and for evaluating the implementation of the DMP.

As per the Grant Agreement (Task 1.1 "Project Management & Financial Administration, including IPR management" subtask 1.1.3) all data in possession of the PC, which will be stored on CNR's, Trust-IT's and

MARIS' servers to be utilised by for the activities foreseen under the Grant Agreement, will be treated in due respect of the European General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.

3. Data Management of aquatic data as used and generated by Blue-Cloud 2026

3.1. The types and formats of data gathered and generated

Data input for the Virtual Labs will be largely gathered and retrieved from the aquatic data infrastructures that are included in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project. Additional input might be added by researchers ingesting data sets from other external sources. Thereafter, researchers may generate data of various kinds using the Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE services.

3.1.1. Data retrieved from existing blue infrastructures

The following aquatic data infrastructures are existing pillars under the current Blue Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service:

- SeaDataNet (physics, bathymetry, geology, chemistry, biology, geophysics);
- EMODnet Bathymetry (bathymetry);
- EMODnet Chemistry (chemistry);
- EurOBIS – EMODnet Biology (marine biodiversity);
- Euro-Argo and Argo GDAC (ocean physics and marine biogeochemistry);
- ELIXIR-ENA (biogenomics);
- EcoTaxa (bio images);
- ICOS-Marine (carbon);
- SOCAT – Surface Ocean CO2 Atlas (carbon).

As part of the WP2 activities in Blue-Cloud 2026, the following aquatic data infrastructures will be added to the federation:

- SIOS (physics, chemistry, biology, geophysics);
- EMODnet Physics (physics);
- MGnify (biogenomics, biodiversity);
- EMSO (physics, geophysics, biology, chemistry).

These infrastructures are developed and operated by research, governmental, and industry organisations from European states, and they have established links to data originators and their data collections,

facilitating to oversee and engage in the process from collection to validation to storage and distribution. Several are also increasingly involved in generating data products and models, which are run by the infrastructure teams or made available as services for external users from research, government and industry. These aquatic data infrastructures are also mostly complementary to each other, dealing with other data originators and/or different stages in the processing chains from data acquisition to data products to knowledge. The infrastructures represent a wide range of data types and formats which are summarised in the following concise table:

Aquatic data infrastructure	Types of data	Formats
SeaDataNet	physical, geological, chemical, biological, bathymetric, and geophysical observation data sets and climatology products	Common Data Index (CDI) metadata format; SeaDataNet ODV4 ASCII, NetCDF (CF), and MedAtlas data formats; Sextant Products Catalogue metadata format; ODV4 ASCII data collection and NetCDF (CF) data product formats
EMODnet Bathymetry	Bathymetric observation data sets and generated DTM data products	Common Data Index (CDI) metadata format; SeaDataNet ODV4 ASCII, and NetCDF (CF) data formats; XYZ, ESRI ASCII, EMODnet EMO, and GeoTIFF formats for DTM products
EMODnet Chemistry	Chemical observation data sets and generated harmonised chemical data collections	Common Data Index (CDI) metadata format; SeaDataNet ODV4 ASCII, and NetCDF (CF) data formats; Marine Litter dedicated ASCII data formats; ODV4 ASCII data collection format
EurOBIS – EMODnet Biology	biogeographic data with focus on taxonomy and distribution records in space and time	IMIS metadata format; Darwin Core data model
Euro-Argo – Argo GDAC	salinity/temperature and biogeochemical observation profiles	NetCDF (CF) data format incl metadata
ELIXIR-ENA	nucleotide sequencing information: covering raw sequencing data, sequence	TSV and JSON compatible metadata formats; EMBL Flatfile data format, FASTA

Aquatic data infrastructure	Types of data	Formats
	assembly information, functional annotation and a host of further data types	data format for sequences; XML data Format
EcoTaxa	images of plankton	TSV and ODV compatible metadata formats; image formats. EcoTaxa (meta)data collections are made available through EuroBIS
ICOS-Marine	long-term oceanic atmospheric observations for carbon	ICOS metadata format; ODV and NetCDFdata formats
SOCAT	long-term oceanic atmospheric observations for carbon	SOCAT metadata format; data is available as individual data set files, regional and global synthesis files and as gridded files in a variety of file formats.
SIOS	focus on processes and their interactions between the different spheres, i.e., biosphere, geosphere, atmosphere, cryosphere, and hydrosphere. The core observational programme provides systematic observations.	GCMD DIF and ISO19115 (using GCMD Science Keywords and OSGeo protocol descriptions). Support for schema.org and DCAT is in progress. EML is supported for harvest.
EMODnet Physics	Brings together oceanphysics metadata and data from EuroGOOS, CMC INSTAC, SeaDataNet, ICES, PANGAEA, PSMSL, SONEL – GNSS, and other networks	Global attributes of the transport format or metadata are included in the ERDDAP dataset. For Delayed Mode data it uses SeaDataNet CDI metadata and ODV + NetCDF data formats. Also, use is made of the OceanSITES data model. Typically, the transport format for operational data is NetCDF (CF Convention).
MGnify	It facilitates the assembly, analysis and archiving of microbiome-derived nucleic acid sequences. For this, it provides access	All metadata relating samples and experiments are inherited from the sequence deposition in

Aquatic data infrastructure	Types of data	Formats
	to taxonomic assignments and functional annotations for analyses covering metabarcoding, metatranscriptomic, and metagenomic datasets, which are derived from a wide range of different environments.	ENA. Additional metadata are incorporated via the EuropePMC metagenomics API supplying metadata from the literature. Also, metadata pertaining to the analysis pipeline are included. For data formats, Research Object Crates (RO-Crates) are in use to store, transfer and display analysis results alongside their provenance metadata. API endpoints primarily return JSON data and can also return tabular (TSV) data; Sequence data are provided in various formats of FASTA file.
EMSO	EMSO high-technology platforms host sensors monitoring various parameters, such as temperature, pH, salinity, water circulation, seabed movements.	Metadata documentation is being created but is currently not available. Data formats include various types supported by ERDDAP, such as .csv, .json, .nc, .xls/.xlsx, .odvTxt, .mat, .mp, .esriAscii, .fgdc, .iso19115, .itx, .tsv.

Table 1 – Aquatic data infrastructures with data types and formats

Selected input will be used in each of the Virtual Labs (VLabs) that will be developed and/or upgraded for the five scientific use cases, as well as for the three WorkBenches for generating EOVS. The Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE is largely based upon the existing Blue-Cloud VRE, powered by the D4Science e-infrastructure, and will be upgraded and expanded by increasing the volume and types of computing resources, federating other e-infrastructures such as from EGI, EUDAT, and WEKEO, and including increased functionalities and services. Adaptation and expansion of the Blue-Cloud VRE environment will be undertaken as part of WP5. The earlier experiences from the pilot Blue-Cloud project will be very useful for these adaptations and upgrading actions which will be done by WP5 in dialogue with WP4, WP3 and WP2. As a result of the communities already supported, a number of facilities for data management are available in the current Blue-Cloud VRE which will be described further in this DMP, where relevant.

The following table gives an overview of the demonstrators and a preliminary indication which types of data they will use. A more detailed overview of data sources is listed in Deliverable 4.1 - V Labs Technical Requirements.

VLab	Data input (expected)	Blue data source (expected)
Common between several demonstrators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CMEMS: sea surface temperature, sea surface height, currents, waves, chlorophyll-a, model outputs ● C3S: meteorology data ● ICOS: carbon data ● EMODnet Chemistry: environmental data ● EMODnet Biology: biodiversity data and products ● EMODnet Chemistry: Chl-a, nutrients and products ● EMODnet Bathymetry: bathymetry ● EMODnet Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EMODnet Physics ● EMODnet Chemistry / SeaDataNet ● EMODnet Biology / EurOBIS ● EMODnet Bathymetry ● ICOS
VLab #1 Coastal oceans observations along Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CMEMS: sea surface temperature, sea surface height, currents, waves, chlorophyll-a, model outputs ● C3S: meteorology/weather model output ● Jerico: currents, temperature, salinity (including from buoys, gliders from IH, SOCIB, PLOCAN) ● EMODnet Physics: currents, waves, river outflows ● EMODnet Geology: Seabed substrate, coastal migration, ● EMODnet Human Activities: vessel density maps ● EMODnet Biology: habitat suitability maps ● EMODnet Bathymetry: bathymetry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EMODnet Physics ● EMODnet Biology ● EMODnet Bathymetry ● Jerico
VLab #2 Coastal currents from observations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CMEMS: currents, sea surface heights ● EMODnet Bathymetry + GEBCO bathymetry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EMODnet Bathymetry

VLab	Data input (expected)	Blue data source (expected)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coastlines from NOAA GSHHG coastline + openstreetmap ECMWF wind speed 	
VLab #3 Carbon-Plankton dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICOS, SOCAT, OCAD: carbon data and fluxes CMEMS / EMODnet physics: Sea surface temperature (including from Buoys of Flemish monitoring network). EMODnet Biology/EurOBIS/LifeWatch: phytoplankton and zooplankton abundances EMODnet Chemistry: Chlorophyll-a, nutrients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMODnet Biology/EurOBIS EMODnet Chemistry ICOS
VLab #4 Marine Environmental Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMEMS: temperature and salinity, sea level anomaly, currents, C3S: wind speed World Ocean Database EMODnet Chemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMODnet Chemistry
VLab #5 Global Fisheries Atlas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fishing catches and efforts from FAO and RFMOs FAO: GRSF 	

Table 2 – Blue-Cloud’s V Labs and their expected data input requirements

Selected input will be used in each of the three WorkBenches developed by the Blue-Cloud team. The following table gives an overview of the Work Benches and a preliminary indication which types of data they will use.

Work Bench	Data input (expected)	Blue data source (expected)
Physical EOvsCMEMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global Ocean- CORA- In-situ Observations Yearly Delivery in Delayed Mode INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_00 1 <p>https://doi.org/10.17882/46219</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMEMS EMODnet physics World Ocean Database SeaDataNet EuroArgo EMSO (optional)

Work Bench	Data input (expected)	Blue data source (expected)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SeaDataNet Temperature and Salinity profiles and time series World Ocean Database temperature and salinity profiles from profiling floats 	
Eutrophication EOVs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMEMS in-situ BGC reprocessed data via Copernicus Marine Service FTP: oxygen, nutrients, chlorophyll EMODnet Chemistry regional datasets for eutrophication World Ocean Database: oxygen, nutrients, chlorophyll 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMEMS: Global Ocean - Delayed Mode Biogeochemical product (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISC_RETE_MY_013_046/services) Eutrophication data collections in the Atlantic - DOI: 10.6092/hmh8-x461
Ecosystem EOVs/EBVs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental data from World Ocean Atlas, ERA5 (surface), Bio-ORACLE and CMEMS, as well as derived products (physical and biogeochemical) Selected model outputs from CMIP6 (physical, biogeochemical) Biological occurrences from GBIF (traditional, genetic, imaging) Biological occurrences and relative abundances from MGnify (genetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMEMS World Ocean Atlas ELIXIR-MGnify ELIXIR-ENA EurOBIS EMODnet Biology GBIF CMIP6

Work Bench	Data input (expected)	Blue data source (expected)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biological occurrences, abundances, biovolume and biomass from OBIS, EMODnet, BODC and others, as pre-processed in ongoing H2020 and HORIZON projects, including AtlantECO and BiOceans5D (traditional, omics, imaging) 	

Table 3 – Blue-Cloud’s WBs and their expected data input requirements

3.1.2. Data inputs from other external sources, retrieved by users

The users of the Blue-Cloud services will be able to upload their own input datasets to complement existing datasets as retrieved from the Blue-Cloud data management infrastructures. As this is completely under the responsibility of the users, no information about the types can be given.

However, to be useful to the users, the own input datasets will have to adopt formats that the Blue-Cloud services are able to handle, thus likely to be of one of the above described formats..

3.1.3. Data generated by users during and after the Blue-Cloud project

The researchers using and running the five Virtual Labs and the three WorkBenches at the Blue-Cloud VRE will generate data products that they will want to store for further use and possibly make available for discovery and access by viewing and downloading. The details of these data products itself are not known yet and will become clearer as part of WP3 and WP4 activities for the development and operation of the scientific VLabs and WorkBenches.

3.2. Reuse of existing data

As indicated in paragraph 3.1, the Blue-Cloud will make use on a major scale of marine data sets which are to be retrieved from aquatic data infrastructures, complemented with aquatic data sets from other sources. The data input can be in-situ data, earth observation data, and model outputs. This way, on a large-scale use and re-use will be made of existing data: use as input for the analyses in the Virtual Labs respectively WorkBenches, and possible re-use for validating and calibrating the Virtual Labs respectively WorkBenches. The data is subject to the data stewardship, the data policies and DMPs of the originating

data repositories, the aquatic data infrastructures. These are mostly in favour of open use and re-use of data sets for various applications, while the licences are used to specify disclaimers and to encourage users to acknowledge used data sources, when publishing their results. Some of the data policies also require registration of users, which is implemented OR realised by logon procedures, not to hamper access but to facilitate tracking and tracing of use and users in respect of the GDPR regulation. A small percentage of aquatic data sets has access restrictions, such as for very costly data sets such as bathymetry and seismic, and sensitive data sets, such as for marine pollutants in selected countries. In those cases, a form of negotiation is required between the users, indicating and motivating its requests, and the data originator.

3.3. Origin of the data

Most data input will comprise marine and inland water data to be retrieved from the aquatic data infrastructures that are represented in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, complemented with such data sets from other sources. These aquatic data infrastructures are leading infrastructures in the European data management landscape and they manage and maintain repositories of data and data products originating from a large number (thousands) of research institutes, national governmental agencies and departments, European and international associations, and industry parties. Their coverage of data and networks of data originators are steadily expanding.

3.3.1. Expected size of the data (if known)

The data offerings from the aquatic data infrastructures represent large data volumes, which are steadily increasing. However, details about their sizes are not easily assessed due to the large numbers and heterogeneity of the data collections. Data set sizes can range from a few Kilobytes (CTD profiles) to many Gigabytes (e.g. satellite images, model outcomes). In a later stage of the project, in particular as part of WP2 activities for further developing the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service, more insights will be gained. This will also apply to the assessment of the sizes of the generated data products, which will become more known during the WP3 and WP4 activities for deploying the Virtual Labs and WorkBenches.

3.3.2. Outline of the data utility and its uses

Federated discovery and access to the aquatic data infrastructures will be arranged by further developing and upgrading the current Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service as part of WP2. This service interacts with the Blue-Cloud VRE and also serves as a standalone service for users interested in discovering and retrieving data sets from the connected aquatic data repositories. The already implemented concept is that the Blue-Cloud data service utility regularly harvests metadata on data collections from each aquatic data infrastructure in order to maintain a common Blue-Cloud metadata catalogue by means of a metadata brokerage mechanism. The resulting metadata catalogue is made

available by means of web services (OGC-CSW) for machine-to-machine interactions, as well as by GUI for human users. The catalogue features a common metadata model with a limited number of metadata tags, including URLs for retrieving additional metadata from the aquatic infrastructures, and an URL to the Blue-Cloud data brokerage mechanism, which handles requests by users for accessing the associated data collections as managed at the aquatic data infrastructures. The data brokerage mechanism interacts with API's (partly already existing and partly to be developed) at each of the aquatic data infrastructures. In practice, the data brokerage might deal with direct download links from fully open data repositories next to dealing with local shopping mechanisms, requiring authentication and authorization. This way, the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service is providing a common interface, both by web services as by GUI, for discovery and retrieval of data collections from the federated aquatic data infrastructures. Users can download and store the retrieved data collections on their own machines or at the data pool environment that is implemented through the Workspace service provided as part of the Blue-Cloud VRE system.

It should be noted that the delivery of data collections initially is done in the existing formats and using vocabularies as offered by each of the blue data infrastructures. A further harmonisation at semantic level is planned as part of WP2 deploying a semantic brokerage service. For analytical processes and for generating data products, activities are ongoing in WP3 and WP4 for analysing, specifying and developing the five Demonstrator Virtual Labs and the three WorkBenches. These Virtual Labs and WorkBenches will be deployed on the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE). The VRE will be largely based upon the existing Blue-Cloud VRE, as deployed in the pilot Blue-Cloud project, powered by the D4Science infrastructure as managed by CNR. This VRE will be adapted and upgraded for the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, adding new services, where needed, and federating multiple e-infrastructures. The Blue-Cloud VRE infrastructure already has a utility for building and maintaining provenance information about the processes as applied for generating specific data products in the Virtual Labs. These include storing information on data input, use and settings of algorithms, and data output into standard PROV records (the PROV standard2 defines a data model, serialisations, and definitions to support the interchange of provenance information on the Web). These provenance records support documenting data products and provide very useful information about the data products for any potential use and reuse performed both by end-users and machine algorithms. They are also very useful for researchers that want to analyse and re-run the analytical processes, possibly changing input or settings for comparisons. Moreover, the current Blue-Cloud VRE infrastructure also has a catalogue service for all data sets and data products as managed for the Virtual Labs. This concerns two catalogues:

- a CSW-compliant catalogue, based on GeoNetwork technology, enabling users to browse and search for geospatial items by relying on the accompanying metadata;

- an SDMX-compliant catalogue, based on Fusion Registry technology – for searching statistical data by relying on their structural metadata;

which are joint in one overall catalogue, based on CKAN technology, which enables users to perform faceted search on the entire set of resources managed by the Virtual Labs. In the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, data input from the aquatic data infrastructures is arranged by bridging between the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service and the Blue-Cloud VRE data pool, which also can be filled by users with data sets from other sources.

Users can be external persons from science, government, and industry, who want to discover and access data sets from the aquatic data infrastructures and/or data products as resulting from the Virtual Labs and WorkBenches. They might want to use these data and data products for a wide range of applications. Internal users are researchers that will have an account on the VRE for specific Virtual Labs and that will undertake activities for deploying, fine tuning, and running the Virtual Labs for different use cases.

3.4. Data Security

The Blue-Cloud technical framework features:

1. the Blue Cloud data discovery and access service component to serve federated discovery and access to aquatic data infrastructures;
2. the Blue Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) component to provide a Blue Cloud VRE as a federation of computing platforms and analytical services. This VRE provides the platform for developing and running the Virtual Labs for the scientific use cases and the WorkBenches for generating EOVs.

Data are and will be safely handled and stored in both components. This is done by relying on repositories operated by MARIS and EUDAT for the Blue-Cloud discovery and access service, whereby MARIS runs the metadata catalogue and related services, while retrieved datasets are temporarily stored at EUDAT for downloading by users or transfer and ingestion into the VRE data pool. That data pool is safely handled in the Blue-Cloud VRE platform, by relying on repositories operated by CNR in the underlying D4Science infrastructure. This way the safety of the data and the accompanying metadata will be secured. Standard practices are in place for this including transparent replication of content across several machines and systematic backup of the content.

In particular, the following strategies for data security are adopted for the Blue-Cloud components:

- Use of high availability storage systems which keep both the data and their enacting system;
- Replicated on-site and off-site, enabling continuous access to systems and data, even after a disaster;
- Use of Hybrid Cloud solutions that replicate both on-site and off-site the main storage systems. This solution provides the ability to instantly fail-over to local on-site hardware all of the storage systems, but in the event of a physical disaster, storage systems can be brought up in additional data centres;
- Backups made at regular intervals of all storage systems (the maximum interval for two consecutive backups is one day); Replication of service to an off-site location, which overcomes the need to restore the service (only the data need to be restored or synchronised).

In addition to preparing for the need to recover systems, precautionary measures can be implemented with the objective of preventing a disaster in the first place. These include:

- local mirrors of systems and/or data and use of disk protection technology such as RAID;
- surge protectors — to minimise the effect of power surges on delicate electronic equipment;
- use of an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) and backup generator to keep systems going in the event of a power failure;
- fire prevention/mitigation systems equipped with alarms and fire extinguishers;
- firewall and network frameworks to avoid intrusion and attacks;
- Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.

Finally, the connection between the Blue-Cloud components is secured with Transport Level Security (TLS) that provides communications security over the computer network. It ensures privacy and data integrity between two communicating computer applications. In particular, any connections between a client (e.g., a web browser) and a Blue-Cloud server have the following properties:

- The connection is private (or secure) thanks to the adoption of the symmetric cryptography to encrypt the data transmitted. The keys for this symmetric encryption are generated uniquely for each connection and are based on a shared secret negotiated at the start of the session. The server and client negotiate the details of which encryption algorithm and cryptographic keys to use before the first byte of data is transmitted. The negotiation of a shared secret is both secure (the negotiated secret is unavailable to eavesdroppers and cannot be obtained, even by an attacker who places themselves in the middle of the connection) and reliable (no attacker can modify the communications during the negotiation without being detected);

- The identity of the communicating parties can be authenticated using public-key cryptography. This authentication can be made optional at client side, but is ensured at the server side;
- The connection ensures integrity because each message transmitted includes a message integrity check using a message authentication code to prevent undetected loss or alteration of the data during transmission;
- The connection ensures forward secrecy, ensuring that any future disclosure of encryption keys cannot be used to decrypt any TLS communications recorded in the past.

These measures will be detailed further during the project when the development of the infrastructure components has progressed.

3.5. Allocation of resources

There are a number of categories of costs to be considered for making Blue-Cloud data and services FAIR. These include:

- **Data input costs:** the input data will be retrieved from the connected aquatic data infrastructures. The costs for getting connected, which can include content and service adaptations for metadata and data retrieval, will be carried by the Blue-Cloud product budget. The cost for operation of the aquatic data infrastructures will fall outside the Blue-Cloud and is to be carried by the data infrastructures themselves. The costs of the operation of the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service, both service and staff resources, will be part of the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure.
- **Data curation costs and costs of data products generation:** the input data as retrieved from the aquatic data infrastructures and other sources might require additional processing and conversions to make the data sets fully fit for the purpose of the analytical services in the Virtual Labs and WorkBenches. Part of these efforts and costs might relate to staff costs of the managers and operators of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure and will be included in the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure. While, another part will be carried out by researchers that are performing analyses using the Virtual Labs and WorkBenches. The activities of the Blue-Cloud scientific teams will be covered by the Blue-Cloud project budget. External users, if allowed within the project stage, will have to bear these costs themselves. The same applies to the costs of performing analyses with the Virtual Labs and WorkBenches to generate data products. The activities of the Blue-Cloud scientific teams within the project duration will be covered by the Blue-Cloud project budget. External users, if allowed within the project stage, will have to bear these costs themselves.

- **Operation costs of Blue-Cloud infrastructure:** these include the costs for operating the different service components of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure such as for storage, catalogue services, analytical processes, and publishing. These are part of the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure and will be covered by the Blue-Cloud project budget during the project lifetime. After the end of the project and for the duration of at least two years, these same costs will be covered by the infrastructure components operated by Blue-Cloud core operators.

Assessing the costs at this stage of the project is not possible, as several new developments and upgrades are planned for the overall Blue-Cloud architecture, the dedicated services, and the organisation of the operations with specific roles for selected Blue-Cloud partners.

The same applies to giving information about future exploitation of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure beyond the Blue-Cloud 2026 project. That will be included in the activities in WP7 for preparing an exploitation and business plan as well as a roadmap to 2030, exploring opportunities both for wider application and expansion of the Blue-Cloud 2026 infrastructure and for funding.

In the project phase, the responsibilities for management of aquatic datasets will be carried jointly by the partners that are involved in WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5.

3.6. FAIR principles

The FAIR concept relates to “Data and services that should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable, both for machines and for people.” The emphasis is on machine FAIRness. In the following paragraphs, the current status for the Blue-Cloud will be described, and reference will be made to activities which are already planned as part of the Blue-Cloud Work Plan and to activities which might be added, for improving FAIRness.

3.6.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data are Findable when they are described by sufficiently rich metadata and registered or indexed in a searchable resource that is known and accessible to potential users. Additionally, a unique and persistent identifier should be assigned such that the data can be unequivocally referenced and cited in research communications. The identifier enables persistent linkages to be established between the data, metadata and other related materials in order to assist data discovery and reuse. Related materials may include the code or models necessary to use the data, research literature that provides further insights into the creation and interpretation of the data and other related information. The data input for the Blue-Cloud VRE and its Virtual Labs are derived mostly from the blue data infrastructures which are represented in the Blue-Cloud project. They are leading in the European marine data management landscape, managing and giving discovery and access to data and data products originating from a large number (thousands) of

research institutes, national governmental agencies and departments, European and international associations, and industry parties. For that purpose, each has developed and is operating their dedicated discovery and access services, applying community standards and principles. Moreover, several of the blue data infrastructures are engaged in activities for analysing and improving their FAIRness, for instance as part of the ENVRI-FAIR or FAIR-EASE projects.

However, in practice different metadata formats and different vocabularies are being applied, which is largely due to existing community differences and history and background of the different initiatives. This situation is gradually changing, under influence of increased cooperation and the push for FAIRness, but also in the future differences will remain and have to be overcome by interoperability, because 'one size fits all' is not feasible and adopting common standards can be quite disruptive and costly for the existing infrastructures, their networks and best practices.

The Blue Cloud data discovery and access service gives federated discovery and access to the blue data infrastructures. This is done by building and maintaining a common Blue-Cloud metadata catalogue, which features a common metadata model with a limited number of metadata tags, to be completed by mappings with each of the metadata services of the blue data infrastructures. The Blue-Cloud common data model focuses on describing data collections by means of fields for What, When, Where, Who, and additional fields for querying more detailed metadata at each source and for facilitating access by means of downloading the associated data sets at granule level from the source infrastructures. The resulting Blue-Cloud metadata catalogue has two levels, consisting of harmonised discovery metadata at collection level, and richer use metadata at data granule level. The first level is tackled by using the GEODAB brokerage service for feeding a common denominator metadata format, using metadata output from the individual BDIs. For the second level, use is made of the individual webservice and APIs from the BDIs to allow for downdrilling from collection level to data granule level.

As part of the Blue-Cloud 2026 activities actions will be directed towards improving and optimising the Data Discovery and Access service by:

- developing and integrating a Semantic Brokerage service in order to harmonise between the vocabularies used by the individual BDIs so that the DD&AS will use common terms;
- In the Blue-Cloud practice it appeared that each of the BDIs makes use of web services or APIs which are quite different in functionality and documentation. Therefore, actions will be directed towards making those services of BDIs more FAIR, so that the machine-to-machine interactions for the metadata and the data brokerage services of the DD&AS will become more streamlined.

The Blue-Cloud VRE is largely based on the existing D4Science e-infrastructure. As part of the pilot Blue-Cloud, a bridge was developed between the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service and the Blue-

Cloud VRE, facilitating the input of retrieved data collections into a VRE data pool. Users are also able to import data sets from other sources into this VRE data pool. The VRE data pool is realised through a family of technologies leveraging cloud-based technologies to deliver high scalability, security, reliability, and availability. To any object stored in it, a unique and persistent identifier is generated and a unique and persistent web locator (PURL) is generated. Versioning is automatically enabled to guarantee persistence also when new versions are incrementally generated and stored.

The D4Science infrastructure provides the kernel for the Blue-Cloud VRE and has already a utility for building and maintaining provenance information about the processes as applied for generating specific data products in the Virtual Labs. Functionality includes storing information on data input, use and settings of algorithms, and data output into standard PROV records (the PROV standard² defines a data model, serialisations, and definitions to support the interchange of provenance information on the Web). These provenance records support to document data products and provide very useful information about the data products for any potential use and re-use performed both by end-users and machine algorithms. They are also very useful for researchers that want to analyse and re-run the analytical processes, possibly changing input or settings for comparisons. Moreover, the D4Science infrastructure already has a catalogue service for all data sets and data products as managed for the Virtual Labs. This concerns two catalogues:

- a **CSW-compliant catalogue**, based on GeoNetwork technology, enabling users to browse and search for geospatial items by relying on the accompanying metadata;
- an **SDMX-compliant catalogue**, based on Fusion Registry technology – for searching statistical data by relying on their structural metadata.

which are joint in one **overall catalogue**, based on CKAN technology, which enables users to perform faceted search on the entire set of resources managed by the Virtual Labs. These existing D4Science services have provided the basis and have been adapted to serve as the so-called Blue-Cloud VRE data catalogue and VRE data pool.

The VRE data catalogue and data pool gives users overview and access to all data sets as included in the VRE as input, but also contains all data products generated in the Virtual Labs. It facilitates VRE researchers to label a subset of their data products for wider publication, which allows to compile automatically a dedicated service to give metadata about and access to public VRE data products. Making data openly accessible

Accessible data objects can be obtained by humans and machines upon appropriate authorisation and through a well-defined and universally implementable protocol. Anyone should be able to access at least

² PROV standard: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

the metadata. It is important to emphasise that Accessible in FAIR does not mean Open without constraint. Accessibility means that the human or machine is provided - through metadata - with the precise conditions by which the data are accessible and that the mechanisms and technical protocols for data access are implemented such that the data and/or metadata can be accessed and used at scale, by machines, across the web. The Blue Cloud data discovery and access service gives federated discovery and access to the blue data infrastructures. The data access part is handled by a Blue-Cloud data brokerage mechanism, developed for handling requests by users for access to the associated data collections as managed at the blue infrastructures. In practice, some blue data infrastructures feature fully open data download links, while some other feature a shopping mechanism, with user login, and possibly making a clear distinction between unrestricted and restricted data. For restricted data, requests require decisions by data originators. While unrestricted data sets are released for downloading immediately, only requiring login for track and tracing purposes, and consenting to the licence of the data. So far, the DD&AS has focused on open data, however, including also services that require identification.

As said earlier, in the pilot Blue Cloud project a lot of differences were encountered and resolved between the web services and API's as published by BDIs for metadata discovery and for access to actual data sets. In the Blue-Cloud 2026 project the objective is to discuss together with the technical representatives of the BDIs more streamlining of those services and improving documentation of those services, where needed. These actions should make the DD&AS functioning more efficient and also should lead to a strengthening of the coherence of web services as offered by the BDIs in the European marine data landscape.

The delivered data follow the formats as provided by the blue data infrastructures.

3.6.2. Making data interoperable

Interoperable data and metadata are described by community and/or domain standards for technical interoperability and vocabularies for semantic interoperability, and they include qualified references to other data or metadata. It is this that allows the data to be 'machine-actionable'. Interoperability is an essential feature in the value and usability of data. Legal interoperability of data has to be considered as well. In FAIR, legal interoperability falls under the principle that data should be 'Reusable'. The delivered data follow the formats as provided by the blue data infrastructures. These formats range from general international standards to specific community standards. In the latter case, these will be fit for specific software as recommended by the blue data infrastructures, while international standards can be handled by a wider range of software tools and services. The blue data infrastructures also make use of specific vocabularies for marking up metadata and data. Information about the formats, vocabularies and appropriate software and services can be found at the portals of the blue data infrastructures. As part of

WP3 and WP4 activities will be undertaken by the research groups to improve the interoperability between data sets, originating not only from the BDIs, but also from external repositories. Use will be made of existing software packages for transforming data formats to other common formats, to be suited for bundling of data sets from different repositories into more common input formats. Existing tools will come from SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, EBI, NOAA, and others. Also, use of common vocabularies in all metadata and data formats is an important prerequisite towards consistency and interoperability. Common vocabularies consist of lists of standardised terms that cover a broad spectrum of disciplines of relevance to the oceanographic and wider community. Using standardised sets of terms solves the problem of ambiguities associated with data markup and also enables records to be interpreted by computers. This opens up data sets to a whole world of possibilities for computer aided manipulation, distribution and long-term reuse. Therefore, as part of the Semantic Brokerage service development in WP2, it will be explored if this can also be used for adopting common vocabularies in WP3 and WP4 developments.

A very good basis for the Semantic Brokerage are the common vocabularies which have been initiated and are maintained by **SeaDataNet** for the marine and oceanographic data community. SeaDataNet (<https://www.seadatanet.org>), one of the Blue-Cloud blue data infrastructures, is a major pan-European infrastructure for managing, indexing and providing access to marine data sets and data products, acquired by European organisations from research cruises and other observational activities in European coastal marine waters, regional seas and the global ocean. Founding partners are National Oceanographic Data Centres (NODCs), major marine research institutes, UNESCO-IOC, ICES, and ECJRC. The SeaDataNet network was initiated in the 1990s and its network of data centres and infrastructure with standards, tools, and services has expanded, inter alia with support of many EU projects. SeaDataNet is also a major infrastructure in the European Marine Observation and Data network (EMODnet) and has an MoU and close cooperation with Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS). SeaDataNet develops, governs, and promotes common standards, vocabularies, software tools, and services for marine data management, which are freely available from its portal and widely adopted and used. The SeaDataNet common vocabularies contains multiple lists of standardised terms that cover a broad spectrum of disciplines of relevance to the oceanographic and wider community. It follows the W3C SKOS specification for encoding data dictionaries and taxonomies served. The SeaDataNet vocabulary services are technically managed and hosted by the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) at the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS2.0). Content governance of the vocabularies is very important and is done by a combined SeaDataNet and MarineXML Vocabulary Content Governance Group (SeaVoX), moderated by BODC, and including many European and international experts. Documentation about the SeaDataNet controlled vocabularies can be found at: <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Common-Vocabularies>

Moreover, the SeaDataNet network of data centres maintains and publishes a series of European directory services which are also widely used for marking up metadata and data:

- European Directory of Marine Organisations (EDMO)
- European Directory of Marine Environmental Data Sets (EDMED)
- European Directory of Marine Research Projects (EDMERP)
- European Directory of Ocean-Observing Systems (EDIOS)
- Cruise Summary Reports (CSR) Documentation about the SeaDataNet Directories can be found at: <https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata>. Both the SeaDataNet controlled vocabularies and SeaDataNet Directories are made available as web services for machines and by means of client interfaces for end-users. The client interfaces provide end-users options for searching, browsing and CSV-format export of selected entries. The machine interfaces are provided via a SOAP API and as SPARQL endpoints.

Identified additional actions for FAIRness

- The adoption of SeaDataNet vocabularies will be considered where mappings are possible and not too extensive in order to contribute to harmonisation of metadata and data, improving the interoperability. This will apply to the planned VRE catalogues both for input data and data products resulting from Virtual Labs.

3.6.3. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

For data to be Reusable, the FAIR principles reassert the need for rich metadata and documentation that meet relevant community standards and provide information about provenance, reporting how data was created and information about consecutive data reduction or transformation processes to make data more usable, understandable or 'science-ready'. The ability of humans and machines to assess and select data on the basis of criteria relating to provenance information is essential to data reuse, especially at scale. Reusability also requires that the data be released with a 'clear and accessible data usage licence': in other words, the conditions under which the data can be used should be transparent to both humans and machines. The data input for the Blue-Cloud VRE and its Virtual Labs and WorkBenches will be derived mostly from the blue data infrastructures which are represented in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project. Each has developed and is operating their dedicated discovery and access services, applying community standards and principles. Moreover, several of the blue data infrastructures are engaged in activities for analysing and improving their FAIRness. In a number of cases, this might include activities for enriching metadata by adding more details about observations and quality control methods applied, which might be done by

linking to other repositories such as the SeaDataNet directories, Ocean Best Practices, published literature repositories, and others.

The Blue-Cloud VRE catalogue aims at publishing data products as generated by the researchers with the Virtual Labs. Their metadata is enriched with the provenance documentation, this way providing users detailed information about the way that the data products were generated, which will be very useful for wider use. And the provenance information gives scientific users detailed information how the data products might be reproduced with the Virtual Labs which is again very useful as it allows VRE users to repeat the same analyses, but for instance changing input and/or settings. The Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service functions with a shopping basket mechanism, whereby each user has to register once. All users can freely query and browse the data catalogue; however, submitting requests for data access via the shopping basket requires that users are logged on. All data requests concern unrestricted data sets. These requests are processed immediately after submission and requested data sets, once retrieved from the blue data infrastructures, are made ready for download. The processing of all data requests is controlled by a Shopping Ledger component which is integrated in the catalogue interfaces. The Shopping Ledger administers and processes all transactions, communicating with the connected blue data infrastructures through the data brokerage service. Users will receive confirmation e-mails of their data set requests and subsequent processing, and can also check progress and undertake data downloading from the Shopping Ledger which is part of their personal dashboard. On their turn, managers from blue data infrastructures are able to follow via the Shopping Ledger all transactions for their data sets online. Each of the blue data infrastructures might have their own data policy and associated licences for use. Those licences will be mentioned in the metadata and will be propagated to users, so that they can look up the prevailing licences.

4. Other Research outputs and datasets generated by the Blue-Cloud 2026 website

The data processing activities inherent to the user activity on the project public website at <https://blue-cloud.org> (i.e., user registration, events management, etc.) which involve the processing of personal data should take into consideration the principles set out under the GDPR; the main principles include:

Lawfulness – As determined by Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR, personal data must be processed lawfully. Under Art. 6 GDPR, lawfulness requires either (i) consent of the individuals whose data is used (“Data subject”) or otherwise some other legitimate basis, such as: (ii) necessity for the performance of a contract to which the Data Subject is party or to take steps at the request of the Data Subject prior to entering a contract, (iii) a legal obligation, (iv) necessity to protect the vital interests of the Data Subject or of another natural

person, (v) necessity for performing a task in the public interest, (vi) necessity for the legitimate interests of the controller or a third party (as long these legitimate interests are not overridden by the interests and the rights of the data subject).

Fairness – Processing of personal data shall always be fair (as determined by Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR), meaning that personal data shall be handled in ways that may be reasonably expected and not use such data in a way that may produce detrimental and unjustified adverse effects on Data Subjects. This principle is also strictly connected with the data protection rights that Data Subjects are entitled to exercise under the GDPR, meaning that the Project shall facilitate the exercise of these rights.

Transparency – The principle of transparency, that is set out under Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR, is strictly connected to the principle of fairness in that it establishes an obligation for the controller to take appropriate measures in order to keep the Data Subjects informed – in an easy and accessible way – about how their personal data will be used. This involves the development of an information notice (or privacy policy) to be provided to Data Subjects following the requirements set out under Art. 13 and Art. 14 GDPR, which prescribes the essential elements of which Data Subjects shall be informed.

Purpose limitation – As determined by Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR, personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes. This obligation aims to ensure openness about the purpose of the processing and to ensure that the processing activities undertaken by the controller are in line with Data Subjects' expectation. In connection with the principle of data minimization, the purpose will also determine what personal data is necessary for the processing.

Data minimization – As determined by Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR, personal data shall be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. It follows from the above that, for each purpose of processing activity, the controller shall identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose.

Accuracy – As determined by Art. 5(1)(d) GDPR, personal data shall be accurate and kept up to date, so as to ensure the quality of the personal data that are collected. The controller is therefore required to ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of the personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to provide Data Subjects with appropriate means to correct and update their own personal data, when needed.

Storage limitation – As determined by Art. 5(1)(e) GDPR, personal data shall be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. It follows from the above that personal data shall not be stored for longer

than actually needed, unless a reason (and a legal basis) for further processing exists. In compliance with this principle, the controller shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from its systems when it no longer has a reason for keeping them or, alternatively, anonymize and aggregate such data until the point they no longer qualify as personal data under the GDPR.

Security (integrity and confidentiality) – As determined by Art. 5(1)(f) GDPR in combination with Art. 32 GDPR, personal data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures.

The table below showcases the main datasets created and managed through the Blue-Cloud 2026 website. Should any more dataset be created in the future, an update of this table and a new release of the document will be provided.

ID	Dataset	Dataset format	Gathered information	Personal data? (Y/N)	Ethical issues? (Y/N)	Dissemination level	Consent gathered	Notes
1	Community DB	Drupal database representation	Name, surname, email, Organisation, Organisation type, Stakeholder category	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use.	The official “Blue-Cloud community” resides in this database, which includes proof of the privacy consent. Users can authenticate to the website via the SSO provided by the D4Science platform. During the authentication phase, the website will receive name, surname and email from the D4Science platform. Once authenticated, the user can complete its profile by adding other data such as Organisation, Organisation type, Stakeholder category. This data will be saved in the Drupal database.
2	Publications (deliverables, milestone reports, specifications, etc.)	pdf	Author information, (name, affiliation)	N	N	ZENODO, Blue-Cloud catalogue, shared on the public website via APIs	Only documents of type “public” will be shared	unique DOI generated by ZENODO
3	Teleconference recordings	video	User personal information registered to an event (name, surname, email)	Y	N	internal use - private	Privacy form. Consent form to photo/video completed	In some cases, recorded information may be processed by the Zoom video-conference system. Despite being a US-based provider, Zoom complies with GDPR requirements, as per their policy, available here

ID	Dataset	Dataset format	Gathered information	Personal data? (Y/N)	Ethical issues? (Y/N)	Dissemination level	Consent gathered	Notes
4	Events (including webinars, workshops and 3rd-party events)	video, csv/excel, pdf	User personal information registered to an event (name, surname, email)	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Consent form to photo/video completed.	In some cases, recorded information may be processed by the Zoom video-conference system. Despite being a US-based provider, Zoom complies with GDPR requirements, as per their policy, available here
5	Events video footage	video	User behaviour during an event	N	N	website, social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)	Consent form to photo/video completed	
6	Live Surveys (mentimeter, Sli.do or similar) at workshops / webinar/ f2f meetings	csv/excel, pdf, report	User personal information as a voter (name, surname, email)	Y	N	website, publications, deliverables (only anonymous data)	Privacy form	Data anonymised before publication
7	Workshop materials	pdf, csv/excel video		Y	Y	ZENODO, Blue-Cloud catalogue		

ID	Dataset	Dataset format	Gathered information	Personal data? (Y/N)	Ethical issues? (Y/N)	Dissemination level	Consent gathered	Notes
						shared on the public website via APIs		
8	User GDPR consents	MySQL database representation	Drupal ID, Drupal username and Drupal email of user in the website, consents given / rejected	Y	N	Trust-IT servers	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use.	Provided by Trust PPG-Tool and stored internally to be GDPR compliant. The tool tracks users' consents and rejections in a way compliant with the GDPR

Table 4- Research outputs and datasets to be generated by Blue-Cloud 2026 website

4.1. Deposition of data, documentation and code

Data collected directly on the website are stored on a relational database management system (RDBMS) MySQL. Drupal documentation and source code are available on www.drupal.org. The specific Blue-Cloud 2026 implementation includes a customised graphical theme which is stored on the Trust-IT servers.

The dataset collected internally, excluding data shared with external services (e.g. Youtube) are stored in Trust-IT servers hosting Blue-Cloud and located on Amazon AWS Cloud (EC2 instances), in the European region of Ireland. The access to the AWS servers is restricted to COMMPla’s staff. The server architecture is described in the figure below.

Architecture on AWS

Figure 1- Servers architecture for Blue-Cloud 2026

4.2. Data access provided in case of restrictions

A limited number of project members have access to the system backend and they can access the information in any case where there are any restrictions. Data access is based on a manual administered RBAC (Role Based Access Control) process.

For the project public website (www.blue-cloud.org) the open framework Drupal ([Drupal 9](#)) has been adopted as Content Management System (CMS). Natively, Drupal supports robust processes to manage access and availability in general in terms of authentication and authorisation to datasets. Access to the Drupal databases is limited only from the server machine where the database is installed and accessible as localhost as well, for security reasons.

The users accessing the data are given dedicated and customised privileges, dependent on their role, and the information is always on-line and available, when needed. The source data from any feedback forms undertaken is not made public or shared outside the consortium. It is only used by the consortium for the purposes of gathering feedback to help improve the platform for future activities.

4.3. Existing data being re-used

Looking at the main datasets created and managed through the Blue-Cloud 2026 website, with respect to publications (deliverables, milestone reports, specifications, etc.) some entries are written as synopsis on a regular basis, and some data is being summarised from existing public reports of interest to the topics related to the EOSC marine community. In the case of curated reports, the source report is always referenced. The source data from surveys undertaken is not made public or shared outside the consortium.

When it is not concerned by the need of exploitation, the data will be aggregated and anonymised in order to have only data statistics without the detailed information regarding the source or any kind of personal information.

For progressing with the project, it is crucial to re-use the data collected to compare/aggregate or simply reach a final goal in the vision of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project (see Section 3.6 FAIR principles).

Regarding the sharing of aggregated data forming the results of this project, whenever possible Blue-Cloud 2026 adopts the following licence for results: **Creative Commons attribution licence CC BY 4.0** for documents, reports, presentations, scientific publications (possibly in diamond open access outlets) etc., unless otherwise agreed amongst the partners for justified reasons. This allows sharing and adaptation of material as long as the work is appropriately attributed.

4.4. Procedures implemented to ensure security and GDPR compliance -

Blue-Cloud 2026 has a [Privacy Policy and Terms of Use Statement](#), for services provided via the project website, which addresses personal data (processing, data subject’s rights, opt-out, cookies used on the website and in social media, etc.). Trust-IT is the data controller regarding all personal data processing carried out through the Website, while all project partners have been identified as Data processors for GDPR purposes and therefore they are allowed to access personal data provided via the Blue-Cloud 2026 website, managed by Trust-IT. For example, Name, contact details and other Personal Data (typically, email, sensitive information regarding gender, or dietary requirements needed for the organisation of events) processed for applications collected via the Blue-Cloud.org website will be kept by Trust-IT as Data Controller in terms of the GDPR for up to 5 years after project completion, also to allow for possible external audits, as requested by contractual provisions the Data Controller is subjected to.

The Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium aims to strike a reasonable balance between security and convenience. Emails are usually sent as unencrypted text. If misrouted or intercepted, an unencrypted email could be read easily. Should a matter that requires **high security or confidentiality** be dealt with by the Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium, Partners are requested to inform Trust-IT beforehand on the sensitivity of the information and they are requested not to send the related information through email. The Project will take measures to prevent data loss and facilitate any security aspects related to the transfer of data and information, as required, by adopting different information transmission protocols (e.g., sending, with a shared transfer, encrypted zip files that are password-protected).

The Blue-Cloud 2026 website adopts security measures consistent with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to protect personal information under its control against loss, misuse, and alteration. In general terms, server configuration, https certificates, access controls, password storage and other relevant elements are dealt with in accordance with the provisions of the GDPR. The main points expressed by GDPR compliance are addressed in Blue-Cloud 2026 indicated in the table below.

GDPR main points	Blue-Cloud 2026 solution to address them
The right to be informed	Privacy Policy and Terms of Use notice (available online at https://blue-cloud.org/privacy-policy)
The right of access	Each profile page shows the consents agreed by the user. Moreover, the user may access and change her/his Personal Data at any time
The right to rectification	Each profile page permits at any time to change the consents agreed by the user and the correction or update of Personal Data where they may be inaccurate or incomplete
The right to erasure	The user may delete her/his own account including the personal data involved

GDPR main points	Blue-Cloud 2026 solution to address them
The right to restrict processing	The user can request the restriction of the processing of her/his Personal Data, where she/he feels that the Personal Data processed is inaccurate, unnecessary or unlawfully processed, or where she/he has objected to the processing
The right to data portability	It is possible to provide data export in CSV format
The right to object	<p>Objection is possible and can be exerted by the user at any point in time. In the privacy notice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individuals are informed of their right to object “at the point of first communication” (namely, in the privacy notice). ● This is “explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject” and is “presented clearly and separately from any other information” (namely, in the privacy notice)
Rights related to automated decision making and profiling	Usually no automated processing of personal data on Drupal
Accountability and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Appropriate technical and organisational measures that ensure and demonstrate that Blue-Cloud complies have been implemented. These include internal data protection policies such as staff training, internal audits of processing activities, and reviews of internal HR policies. ● Relevant documentation on processing activities is maintained in the campaign activities that are carried out. ● Trust-IT has appointed a DPO (see Section 4.1) ● Measures that meet the principles of data protection by design and data protection by default have been implemented following the 7 step methodology suggested by the Norwegian Data Protection Authority /4/ as a best practice to address Art. 25 of the GDPR. In particular, for step 4, “coding”, the use of Drupal provides a strong foundation of ‘security-by-design’ principles. ● Security features will be improved on the future releases of the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform and, if needed, on an ongoing basis.
Breach notification	<p>The Data Controller shall notify the relevant supervisory authority of a breach where it is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals. In case of data breach, the notification will be sent within 72 hours to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Italian national authority (Garante per la protezione dei dati personali - www.garanteprivacy.it, piazza Venezia, 11 - Roma). 2. Commission de la protection de la vie privée, Rue de la Presse, 35, 1000 Bruxelles.

GDPR main points	Blue-Cloud 2026 solution to address them
	Additionally, the EC and the Blue-Cloud 2026 Data Processors will be informed.

Table 5 - Main points expressed by GDPR compliance

4.5. Website Cookies

The Blue-Cloud 2026 website, to be compliant with the GDPR law in terms of Cookies, shows all the information on cookies that are being used and exploited, presenting the end-user the choices she/he is entitled to. There are some **technical cookies** that are strictly necessary for the navigation of the website and their use cannot be rejected. In case the end-user disagrees with them, she/he will not be allowed to properly navigate the Blue-Cloud 2026 website.

Blue-Cloud is using **measurement cookies** provided by Google Analytics and in the specific for the Google Tag Manager. These cookies can be deactivated by the end-user and the navigation is going to be not seen by Google Analytics. The reason for these cookies is that usage of these types of data is extremely useful to conduct quantitative research in order to disseminate project results and to reach out to target stakeholders with personalised messages and quality information.

The Blue-Cloud website also uses **third-party cookies** – i.e.cookies from websites / web servers other than Blue-Cloud’s. These third parties will either act as independent data controllers regarding their own cookies (using the data they collect for their own purposes and under terms defined by them, e.g. project’s social media) or as data processors for Trust-IT srl (processing personal data onTrust-IT srl’s behalf, e.g. MailJet). For further information on how these third parties may use your information, please refer to their privacy policies:

- LinkedIn
- Twitter
- MailJet
- YouTube

The Cookie policy for the public website is available at <https://blue-cloud.org/privacy-policy-blue-cloud>.

5. Other Research outputs and datasets to be generated by the Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE

The Blue-Cloud VRE is accessible via the Blue-Cloud Gateway at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/>. Data collected on the Blue-Cloud VRE are governed by three essential policies document:

- the Cookie policy;
- the Privacy policy;
- the Terms of Use;

The Cookie policy is a document containing a list of all the cookies used on a website, along with detailed information about each. It also helps users understand how their data is used, how long the cookies will remain on their device and more. A cookie policy isn't the same as a privacy policy.

The Privacy policy is a statement or legal document that discloses how the Blue-Cloud VRE gathers, uses, discloses, and manages users' personal data.

The Terms of Use (a.k.a Terms and Conditions) agreement sets out what's expected from the provider and the users. The agreement is intended to regulate how the VRE manages the users' activity and expectations and also indicates how to protect the VRE from legal issues and illegal behaviours.

All policy documents are not only compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679). Rather they cover exploitation from users outside Europe that are subject to other regulations too.

5.1. The Blue-Cloud VRE cookie policy

This Gateway uses cookies to improve the users' experience while navigating the website. Out of these cookies, the cookies that are categorised as necessary are stored on your browser as they are essential for the working of basic functionalities of the website.

Necessary cookie	Type	Duration	Description
LFR_SESSION_STATE_20158	https	session	LFR_SESSION_STATE_* cookies are created and managed from client-side javascript and they are used only for controlling timestamp of user session expiration.

Necessary cookie	Type	Duration	Description
JSESSIONID	https	session	The JSESSIONID cookie is used by New Relic to store a session identifier so that New Relic can monitor session counts for an application.
COOKIE_SUPPORT	https	46 years 7 months 13 days 3 hours	This cookie is set by the Liferay. This cookie is used for verifying whether the visitor browser support cookies.
GUEST_LANGUAGE_ID	https	46 years 7 months 13 days 3 hours	This cookie is used to store the visitors preferred language ID.
cky-active-check	https	1 day	CookieYes sets this cookie to check if the consent banner is active on the website.
cookieyesID	https	1 year	CookieYes sets this cookie as a unique identifier for visitors according to their consent.
cky-consent	https	1 year	The cookie is set by CookieYes to remember the users's consent settings so that the website recognizes the users the next time they visit.
cookieyes-necessary	https	1 year	CookieYes sets this cookie to remember the consent of users for the use of cookies in the 'Necessary' category.

Necessary cookie	Type	Duration	Description
cookieyes-functional	https	1 year	CookieYes sets this cookie to remember the consent of users for the use of cookies in the 'Functional' category.
cookieyes-analytics	https	1 year	CookieYes sets this cookie to remember the consent of users for the use of cookies in the 'Analytics' category.

Table 6 – Necessary cookies for the Blue-Cloud 2026 website

The Gateway also uses third-party cookies that help us to analyse and understand how users exploit the Blue-Cloud VRE. These cookies are stored on users’ browsers with their consent to do so. Users also have the option to opt out of these cookies, but opting out of some of these cookies may affect the browsing experience.

Functional cookies help to perform certain functionalities like sharing content, collecting feedback, and other third-party features.

Cookie	Type	Duration	Description
ckan_hide_header	http	session	Tailor the Catalogue header to the user role
ckan	http	session	Catalogue preferences

Table 7 – Cookies for the Blue-Cloud 2026 website

Analytical cookies are used to understand how visitors interact with the Gateway. These cookies help provide information on metrics such as the number of visitors, bounce rate, traffic source, etc.

Analytical Cookie	Type	Duration	Description
_ga	https	2 years	The _ga cookie, installed by Google Analytics, calculates visitor, session and campaign data and also keeps track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookie stores information

Analytical Cookie	Type	Duration	Description
			anonymously and assigns a randomly generated number to recognize unique visitors.
_gid	https	1 day	Installed by Google Analytics, _gid cookie stores information on how visitors use a website, while also creating an analytics report of the website's performance. Some of the data that are collected include the number of visitors, their source, and the pages they visit anonymously.
_gat	https	1 minute	This cookie is installed by Google Universal Analytics to restrain request rate and thus limit the collection of data on high traffic sites.

Table 8 – Analytical Cookies for the Blue-Cloud 2026 website

The Cookie Policy for the Blue-Cloud Gateway is accessible to all users at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/cookie-policy>.

5.2. The Blue-Cloud VRE privacy policy

Among the types of Personal Data that this VRE collects, by itself or through third parties, are Cookies; Usage Data; first name; last name; email address; IP address.

Complete details on each type of Personal Data collected are provided in the dedicated sections of the privacy policy or by specific explanation texts displayed before the Data collection.

Personal Data may be freely provided by the User, or, in the case of Usage Data, collected automatically when using this Application.

Unless specified otherwise, all Data requested by the VRE is mandatory, and failure to provide this Data may make it impossible for the VRE to provide its services. In cases where the VRE specifically states that some Data is not mandatory, for example, for some cookies, Users are free not to communicate this Data without consequences to the availability or the functioning of the Service.

Users who are uncertain about which Personal Data is mandatory are welcome to contact the Owner.

Any use of Cookies – or other tracking tools – by the VRE or by the owners of third-party services used by the VRE serves the purpose of providing the Service required by the User, in addition to any other purposes described in the Privacy policy document and in the Cookie Policy.

Users are responsible for any third-party Personal Data obtained, published or shared through this VRE and confirm that they have the third party's consent to provide the Data to the D4Science infrastructure operating the Blue-Cloud VRE.

The Data is processed at the D4Science operating offices and in any other places where the parties involved in the processing are located. All D4Science places are located in Italy, and Data are never transferred to other countries or outside the European Union for any reason not explicitly authorised by the User.

Personal Data are processed and stored for as long as required by the purpose they have been collected for. Therefore:

- Personal Data collected for purposes related to the provision of a VRE service to the User shall be retained until such service has been exploited by the User. For example, a user registration to a VLab is retained until the user is a member of that VLab;
- Personal Data collected for the purposes of the D4Science accounting and monitoring needs are retained as long as needed to fulfil such purposes. Users may find specific information regarding the legitimate interests pursued by D4Science within the relevant sections of this document or by contacting the D4Science office.

Once the retention period expires, Personal Data shall be deleted. Therefore, the right to access, the right to erasure, the right to rectification and the right to data portability cannot be enforced after the expiration of the retention period.

Users may exercise certain rights regarding their Data processed by the D4Science infrastructure.

In particular, Users have the right to do the following:

- Withdraw their consent at any time. Users have the right to withdraw consent where they have previously given their consent to the processing of their Personal Data.
- Object to processing of their Data. Users have the right to object to the processing of their Data if the processing is carried out on a legal basis other than consent. Further details are provided in the dedicated section below.
- Access their Data. Users have the right to learn if Data is being processed by D4Science, obtain disclosure regarding certain aspects of the processing and obtain a copy of the Data undergoing processing.

- Verify and seek rectification. Users have the right to verify the accuracy of their Data and ask for it to be updated or corrected.
- Restrict the processing of their Data. Users have the right, under certain circumstances, to restrict the processing of their Data. In this case, the Owner will not process their Data for any purpose other than storing it.
- Have their Personal Data deleted or otherwise removed. Users have the right, under certain circumstances, to obtain the erasure of their Data from the Owner.
- Receive their Data and have it transferred to another controller. Users have the right to receive their Data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and, if technically feasible, to transmit it to another controller without any hindrance. This provision is applicable provided that the Data is processed by automated means and that the processing is based on the User's consent, on a contract of which the User is part or on pre-contractual obligations thereof.
- Complain. Users can bring a claim before their competent data protection authority.

Any requests to exercise User rights can be directed to D4Science through the following contact: privacy@d4science.org. These requests can be exercised free of charge and will be addressed by D4Science as early as possible and always within one month.

The complete Privacy policy is accessible from the VRE gateway homepage and at the following address: <https://www.iubenda.com/privacy-policy/441050/legal>.

5.3. The Blue-Cloud VRE terms of use

The Blue-Cloud VRE is accessible via the Blue-Cloud Gateway at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/>. The Gateway is operated by D4Science. The content and information made available through this Gateway are available under terms described in the metadata accompanying each product (e.g. "licence" or "constraints" field). Except where otherwise noted (i.e. in case of the primary requirement to comply with the content provider's policy) this is the Creative Commons License.

All derivative products produced and made publicly available through the Blue-Cloud VRE are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) except where otherwise noted.

Upon registration to the Blue-Cloud VRE, the user can immediately use the storage space via the Workspace Service, the Social Networking Collaborative Platform including the Email Service to send/receive content to other registered users, the Social Service to share and read news and posts with your connections and the Notification Service for user notifications, and the Catalogue Service to browse available datasets, methods, and services therein published. The User can also apply to one or more moderated or public Virtual Laboratories (V Labs) offering one or more additional services.

All the Services made accessible through the Blue-Cloud VRE are also accessible through APIs by specifying the secure token generated with the registration and specialised for each VLab the user is a member of. Starting from January 1st 2020, the APIs are exploitable only by using the secure and encrypted communication protocol over a computer network, HTTPS, while the support for the deprecated communication protocol over a computer network, HTTP, is definitely terminated on December 31st 2019.

The user owns the information, content, and method she provides to the D4Science Infrastructure through the Blue-Cloud VRE under this Agreement and may request its deletion at any time unless the user has shared information, content, or method with others and they have not deleted it, or it was copied or stored by other users. Additionally, the user grants D4Science.org a nonexclusive, worldwide, assignable, sublicensable, fully paid up and royalty-free right to us to copy, prepare derivative works of, improve, distribute, publish, remove, retain, add, process, analyse, and use in any way now known or in the future discovered, any information, content, or method you explicitly share or publish, directly or indirectly to D4Science.org, including, but not limited to, any user-generated content, techniques or data to the services without any further consent, notice and/or compensation to you or to any third parties to serve the purpose of providing the service required by the User. Any information you submit to us is at your own risk of loss, as noted in the following sections of this Agreement.

By sharing information, content, or method with the Blue-Cloud VRE, the user represents and warrants that she is entitled to share the information, content, or method and that the information, content, or method is accurate, not confidential, and not in violation of any contractual restrictions or other third-party rights.

The user must promptly notify the D4Science.org Team of any breach of security related to the Services, including but not limited to the unauthorised use of a password or account. To help ensure the security of your password or account, the user should sign out from her account at the end of each session.

The D4Science.org Team, hereafter referred to as D4Science.org, may terminate any user account under the terms of service if the user fails to log in to her account for six months. Moreover, if the user is found to violate our policies at any time, as determined by the D4Science.org in its sole discretion, D4Science may warn the user or suspend or terminate her account.

In the following table, the conditions of use of the main actions.

Action	Conditions of use
Posting Content or Method	<p>You can post content or method to any service made accessible through this Gateway only if (a) you created and own the rights to the content or method or you have the owner’s express permission to post the content or method; and (b) the content or method does not infringe any other person’s or entity’s rights (including the copyrights, trademarks, or privacy rights) or violate any applicable laws, this Terms of Use, Privacy Policy, our Community Best Practices, or any other posted policies. D4Science.org can remove content or methods for any infringing reason.</p> <p>When you use a service to upload content or register a method into a VRE, you retain the irrevocable, exclusive, worldwide right and licence to use, reproduce, modify, display, remix, redistribute, create derivative works, and syndicate your content or method in any medium and through any service. Only where you have specifically shared, or used a specialised service for sharing content will your content become part of a derivative work to be licensed under a schema the owner selects.</p>
Sharing Content or Method	<p>D4Science.org offers sharing and publication at different levels: within a VRE, among different VREs and by publication to data repositories that may be accessible to external users.</p> <p>Each shared content is associated with a copyright licence. A CC BY 4.0 licence is proposed if the dataset is obtained with a mash-up process from different sources (a true derivative product), any other licence (not technically supported by the D4Science Infrastructure) in case of an unaltered product shared with other Users/VREs. In both cases, the metadata must be filled (if not automatically compiled), and a preferred citation must be indicated.</p> <p>You are responsible for any content or method you post to our Services and the consequences of sharing such content or method with others or the general public. This includes, for example, any personal information, any confidential data or any</p>

	<p>unofficial data. D4Science.org is not responsible for the consequences of sharing or posting any personal or other information on its services.</p> <p>When you use a Service that allows users to share, transform, readapt, modify, or combine the content or method with other content or methods, you grant D4Science.org and our Users a non-exclusive, royalty free, worldwide right and licence to [use, reproduce, modify, display, remix, perform, distribute, redistribute, adapt, promote, create derivative works, and syndicate] your content or method [in any medium and through any form of technology or distribution] and to permit any derivative works to be licensed under these same licence terms.</p> <p>Any user accessing shared content must behave according to the copyright licence of the dataset. However, the D4Science Infrastructure does not control or audit access to and/or audit the use of shared content. It can, therefore, not impose a shared policy, but can encourage sharing according to best practices.</p> <p>Sharing content or methods within the D4Science infrastructure (i.e. sharing through one or more VREs) will make them accessible only to authorised users and cannot be accessed from outside.</p>
Publishing Content	<p>The VRE authorised Users can publish content and make it available to the public, exposing it to a general view with no restrictions except for a registration procedure that may be required. Each published set of content is associated with a copyright licence. Published content can be accessed by the general public through this Gateway and through dedicated web applications (e.g. web services).</p>
Secondary Use of the Content	<p>Data accessed through this Gateway do not, and should not, include controls over its end use. However, the content owner or authoritative source for the content must retain version control of the content accessed.</p>

	<p>Once the content has been downloaded from the Gateway, D4Science.org cannot vouch for its quality and timeliness. D4Science.org cannot vouch for any analyses conducted with the content retrieved from the Gateway.</p>
<p>Derivative Work and Data Citation</p>	<p>Derivative work should only be produced by complying with the terms and conditions established in the licence of the used content.</p> <p>The derivative work is owned by the legitimate copyright holder identified among the contributors co-owning the new product. It is the contact point for any use, re-use/re-distribute request.</p> <p>Derivative work may contain content retrieved from the D4Science Infrastructure.</p> <p>Every content should include in its metadata at least a preferred citation, a reference to the infrastructure source dataset and its generation date, and the date that content was accessed or retrieved from the Gateway or any of its services. If the content was a composition of multiple datasets with different citations, the content owner should have added that to the relevant metadata.</p> <p>If such derivative work is produced through VREs, the D4Science Infrastructure generates a default provenance metadata, which matches references to sources used for the derivative work and their respective citations.</p> <p>You must clearly state that “D4Science.org cannot vouch for the analyses derived from this content after it has been retrieved from the D4Science Infrastructure”.</p>

Table 9 – Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE conditions of use

The complete Terms of Use of the Blue-Cloud VRE is accessible from the VRE gateway homepage and at the following address: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/terms-of-use>.

6. SSO & user integration between the Blue-Cloud VRE and the public website

Single-Sign-On (SSO) is an authentication scheme allowing users to log in with a single digital identity to any of several related yet independent services on the Web. True single sign-on allows users to log in once and access services without re-entering authentication factors multiple times. Blue-Cloud 2026 enables SSO between the Blue-Cloud VRE gateway and the Blue-Cloud website. The integration of the SSO mechanism and user integration between the Blue-Cloud VRE and the public Blue-Cloud website aims at enhancing user convenience, facilitate seamless access to resources, and streamline data management processes across these platforms.

The Data is processed at the D4Science operating offices and in any other places where the parties involved in the processing are located. All D4Science places are located in Italy, and Data is never transferred to other countries or outside the European Union for any reason not explicitly authorised by the User. The connection between the Blue-Cloud VRE and the public website exploits secure data exchange protocols and mechanisms, adhering to data protection regulations, to ensure data integrity and privacy. It uses encryption techniques and access controls to safeguard data within each platform, enabling data sharing without compromising user privacy. To ensure the security and privacy of user data during the SSO and user integration, the following measures are in place:

- *encryption and secure communication*: strong encryption algorithms and secure communication protocols (e.g., HTTPS) to encrypt data transmissions between the platforms, preventing unauthorised access and ensuring data confidentiality during transfer;
- *access control and user permissions*: granular access control mechanisms to regulate user access to sensitive data and functionalities. Users will only be granted access based on their defined roles and permissions within each platform;
- *compliance with EU Data Protection Regulations*: adherence to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), by implementing appropriate privacy safeguards, obtaining user consent where necessary, and ensuring transparency regarding data handling practices.

7. Ethical aspects

In this stage of the project it is not possible to identify legal or ethical issues concerning the data that will be handled as input for the Blue-Cloud and the data products that will be generated using the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs.

The Blue-Cloud project is not explicitly dealing with any activity related with personal data collection. Only as part of the registration of users for the operation of the Blue-Cloud catalogues and for creating accounts at the Blue-Cloud VRE information will be gathered of users and their activities. These uses and measures for securing these personal data is clearly explained to users that register for these services (see <https://blue-cloud.org/privacy-policy> for the Blue-Cloud public website and <https://www.iubenda.com/privacy-policy/441050> for the D4Science infrastructure) in accordance with the GDPR. The Privacy Policy at the Blue-Cloud portal includes a Data Protection Notice and a reference to the Cookies Policies (<https://blue-cloud.org/privacy-policy-blue-cloud> and <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/cookie-policy>) is also noticed at the homepage. Finally, the Terms of Use (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/terms-of-use>) clarify all the policies regulating the usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud services. It will be annotated and extended along the time with the specification of the policies associated with the new Blue-Cloud services.

Moreover, specific surveys might be undertaken by the Blue-Cloud project, which will collect personal data. These will be treated again in the most appropriate and secure way and users will be well informed about this approach.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable sets out the main processes and procedures followed by the Blue-Cloud consortium in terms of data management. In particular, the document highlights the following aspects:

- **CNR** assumes the role of **Data Controller** of any personal data gathered, via the **D4Science** platform, **Trust-IT** assumes the role of **Data Controller** for any personal data gathered, via the Blue-Cloud 2026 **website**, **MARIS** assumes the role of **Data Controller** for any personal data gathered, via the Blue-Cloud 2026 **Data Discovery and Access Service**.
- Each Project Partner will assume the role of **Data Processor**, according to the GDPR.
- Data processes and procedures have been designed to be GDPR-compliant.
- FAIR data principles are followed by the Blue-Cloud consortium in managing data.

It is agreed among all Project Partners that this document will be updated whenever changes are made to any of the topics described herein.